

FIRST USE OF FRP REINFORCEMENT BARS IN URUGUAY: DESIGN AND EXPERIMENTAL TESTING OF FRP REINFORCED BEAMS AND COMPARISON WITH CONVENTIONAL STEEL REINFORCED BEAMS.

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ABSTRACT

Fiber Reinforced Polymer (FRP) reinforcement bars are being increasingly used around the world. Despite other applications of FRP materials, there are no bibliographic references of applications of this technology in Uruguay. This experimental project was designed with the aim of helping introduce them, comparing the behaviour of Glass FRP (GFRP) and steel as concrete reinforcement (RC). Three reinforced concrete beams were made with GFRP flexural reinforcement, and three with steel flexural reinforcement. The beams were 3.5 metres long and the cross-section was rectangular (0.15m x 0.30m). Beams were tested under a four points flexural set-up. Cross-sections of both types were designed to fail at the same load. Displacement of the central point (with LVDT's), cracking pattern, failure load and failure mode of the beams were registered during the test. Results showed that both types of beams reached the ultimate design load (around 60 kN). However, as expected, displacements of the GFRP beams were larger (around 6 times) than the steel beams. Moreover, the deformation of the beams, predicted according to ACI 440.1R-15, was in good agreement with the experimental results. Hence, GFRP bars can be used as a substitute of the flexural steel reinforcement in RC structures, even though serviceability conditions may govern the design.

KEYWORDS

FRP reinforced concrete, GFRP bars, steel reinforced concrete, four points flexural test, experimental characterization / investigation

INTRODUCTION

The use of Fiber Reinforced Polymer (FRP) materials is very extended worldwide in non-civil uses in the aerodynamical and automotive industries. In civil engineering, FRP bars are being increasingly used for structural purposes around the world since its appearance during the last years of the past century. In countries such as Japan, China, European Nations, the United States and Canada it is possible to find constructions made with this material.

In Uruguay, FRP materials have been mainly used for non-structural purposes, included the mentioned automotive industry, and others such as telephone booths and fences around electrical equipment. In civil structures, there have been applications of external FRP sheets used in maintenance, reinforcement or repairs of structures. However, there are no bibliographic references of uses of FRP bars as an internal concrete reinforcement in Uruguay.

In that context, this experimental project is presented as a first approach to the use of FRP bars in the country, in order to take advantage of the benefits of the application of this material, namely: its non-corrosive properties, the electromagnetic neutrality, the workability advantages related to its light weight, easy cuttability and reduction of wastes, and even the fact that can be a more environmentally friendly material than steel. Regarding the last advantage, the country has made a big effort during the recent years to reduce its carbon footprint.

The aim of this work is to compare the general behaviour of GFRP and steel reinforced beams. GFRP reinforced concrete beams and steel concrete reinforced beams were designed to reach the same failure load under a four-points flexural test. The cracking pattern and failure modes were registered and analysed. A prediction of the displacement of the central point was made in order to compare with the result of the test. Fib bulletin 40 (FIB, 2007) and ACI 440.1R-15 (ACI, 2015) were used as main bibliography for this project, both as background and to get theoretical models for the design and calculation.

METHODOLOGY

Two types of beams were used in the study: Reference beams (Ai), which used conventional steel reinforced concrete, and concrete beams where the longitudinal reinforcement was replaced by GFRP (Fi). Three samples were made for each type to study repeatability. The number ($i=1, 2, 3$) in the beam sample indicates the individual beams. The beams nominal Length was 3,5 m. The cross-section width was 150 mm and the height 300 mm.

Two 12 mm diameter steel bars and two 10 mm diameter GFRC bars were used as main reinforcement in the Reference and in the GFRC beams, respectively (Figure 1). Main reinforcement was designed to achieve a flexure failure at the beams at a load around 60 kN. At this load, concrete crushing was expected at the GFRC beams and yielding of the steel at the reference beam.

Figure 1. a) Beam cross-section; b) preparation of reinforcement for construction.

All the beams included three 6 mm steel bars as longitudinal construction reinforcement, and 6 mm diameter stirrups (spaced 200 mm). Reinforcement cover was 20 mm. Mean compressive strength was $f_c = 28$ MPa, evaluated on two cylinders. GFRP properties, according to the product datasheet, were Young's Modulus: $E_f = 50$ GPa; and Tensile strength: $f_t = 1000$ MPa. Steel properties were Young's Modulus: $E_s = 200$ GPa; and Tensile strength: $f_s = 500$ MPa. To production of the specimens was made by a construction company on a construction site.

The beams were tested up to failure under four-point bending, i.e. two-point loads of equal magnitude were applied in order to achieve a section between them subjected to pure bending moment. The span between supports was 2.7 m, and the span between applied loads was 0.7 m, as shown in Figure 2.

Beams were placed with the main reinforcement in the bottom side, so this layer was in the tensile side. The loads were applied uniformly across the width of the specimens by a Universal Testing Machine and measured by means of a load cell. A picture of the test set-up is shown in Figure 3. Two LVDT's displacement transducers were placed to measure the deflection in the centre of the span (Figure 3b). LVDT's were mounted on a rigid frame, which was sitting on top of the specimen with its support feet over the position of the specimen's support.

Figure 2. Schematic representation of flexural test set-up

Figure 3: Beam test set-up.

The test was controlled by the stroke displacement, with different stroke speeds (v_i) in two stages: $v_1 = 1 \text{ mm/min}$, from the beginning of the test until reaching 6 mm of mid span descent (in this stage, the element started cracking); $v_2 = 2 \text{ mm/min}$ until failure or end of measuring capacity. During test, the stroke displacement was stopped at regular intervals, when the cracking pattern was drawn over the beam.

RESULTS

Experimental results

The Load vs displacement curves of all the GFRP (F1, F2 and F3) and the steel (A1, A2 and A3) beams are shown in Figure 4 in clear lines. The mean of each type of beam is also displayed on the graphic in darker lines (F_m and A_m).

Figure 4: Load-Displacement curves for the two types of samples: a) complete plots b) detail of initial displacements.

Both types of beams have similar behaviour in the first branch of the graphic (Figure 4b). This is because the bending moment in the beams are below the cracking moment and the stiffness is controlled mainly

by the concrete section. But after the section cracks and the stiffness of the section is controlled by the reinforcement, the deflections of the GFRP beams increase more for the same load increase than in steel reinforced elements.

The slope of the linear adjustment of the Am and Fm cracked section branch are 5.00 kN/mm ($R^2 = 0.996$) and 0.87 kN/mm ($R^2 = 0.999$) respectively. This means that displacements generated by the same load increase are 5,7 times larger in the GFRP beams than in the steel reinforced beam, which was expected, due to the difference in the elasticity modulus of the steel ($E_s = 200 \text{ GPa}$) and the GFRP ($E_f = 50 \text{ GPa}$).

The failure load of each of the tested beams is shown in Table 1. As it can be seen, all the beams reached the design failure load (60 kN).

Table 1: Failure load and bending moment of each tested beam

Beam	Failure load (kN)	Mean (kN)	CV	Failure bending moment (kNm)
F1	66.6	64.5	5%	33.3
F2	60.8			30.4
F3	66.0			33.0
A1	61.2	67.3	13%	30.6
A2	63.3			31.6
A3	77.5			38.7

The final cracking pattern of beam F1 is shown in Figure 5. This was processed and drawn for each beam, as shown in Figure 6. Both types of beams present pure flexure vertical cracks in the central 70 cm of the beams. Outside this central span, cracks tend to slope because of the shear force, as expected according to the bending moment and shear force diagrams. It can also be seen that the crack separation is larger in the FRP reinforced beams than in the steel reinforced beams. Mean crack separation computed is shown in Table 2. The mean crack separation of the GFRP reinforced beams resulted 1,55 times larger than in the steel reinforced beam. It was also observed that the crack width was larger in GFRC beams.

Figure 5 also shows the general appearance of the beam. Some surface imperfections, like stone pockets, can be seen at the bottom of the beams. The poor quality of the concrete may be due to a stiff consistency of concrete or to a lack of compaction during the casting.

Figure 5: Final cracking pattern of beam F1

Figure 6: Final cracking pattern of beams.

Table 2: Mean crack separation of the beams

Beam	Mean crack separation (cm)	Mean (cm)	C.V.
F1	16.4	16.6	13%
F2	18.8		
F3	14.5		
A1	11.4	10.7	7%
A2	10.7		
A3	10.0		

Finally, the failure mode of the GFRP reinforced beams was studied. An example is shown in Figure 7. The cracks show that the beam failure occurred as expected on the compression side of the beam. It took place close to the load application point, where the bending moment and the shear force were maximum. The horizontal cracks indicate that the failure can be produced by concrete crushing, as expected by the design. These horizontal cracks connect with an inclined flexural-shear crack, so shear force may be involved in the rupture of the beam.

Figure 7: Failure mode of beam F2.

Theoretical results

The design of the GFRP beams was made according to ACI440.4R-15 (ACI, 2015). They are designed to fail by the limit state of concrete crushing in flexure. Displacement of the central point was predicted as suggested in the mentioned guide, with a Load-Displacement formulation based on an equivalent moment of inertia obtained from the integration of curvature over its length (Bischoff, 2011a).

The theoretical formulation used depends on the cracking moment of the section. The calculation of the displacements was done using two different hypothesis for this value: Model 1) Obtaining the bending tensile strength of concrete according to ACI440.1R-15 (ACI, 2015) ($f_{ct,fl} = 3.25 \text{ MPa}$), which led to a cracking bending moment of $M_{cr1} = 7.32 \text{ kNm}$; and Model 2) Obtaining the mean cracking moment from the tested beams ($M_{cr2} = 5.30 \text{ kNm}$). The difference between these values may be caused by the previously mentioned lower quality of the concrete at the bottom of the beams, which resulted in a lower tensile strength than the expected by the bibliography.

The theoretical load-displacement plots are shown in Figure 8. At1 and Ft1 represents the results obtained with Model 1 and At2 and Ft2 the obtained with Model 2, both for the steel and FRP reinforcement respectively. Mean experimental values are also plotted in the figure.

Figure 8: Comparison between theoretical model and mean experimental results of Load-Displacement curves: a) complete plots b) detail of serviceability loads.

The graphic shows that the theoretical calculation is in good agreement with the experimental results. The error of the theoretical models for two different loads is shown in Table 3. In general, models used for steel beams have less relative error than the ones used for FRP beams. In both, the cracking moment used for the calculation of displacements has a strong influence in the results, with larger errors of the theoretical models near the load levels corresponding to the cracking moments. Also, larger errors in the cracking moment definition are related to larger errors in higher load levels.

For the FRP beams, the model gets closer to the result when the mean cracking moment of the beams (Model 2: Ft2) is considered. On the other hand, for the steel beam, Model 1 (At1) gets closer to the result.

Table 3: Relative error of theoretical models for $P = 20\text{ kN}$ and $P = 40\text{ kN}$.

Model	Displacement for load $P = 20\text{ kN}$ (mm)	Relative error (%)	Displacement for load $P = 40\text{ kN}$ (mm)	Relative error (%)
Am	1.65	-	5.50	-
At1	1.73	5	5.72	4
At2	2.39	45	6.19	13
Fm	11.50	-	34.00	-
Ft1	5.79	50	24.79	27
Ft2	9.64	16	27.51	19

CONCLUSIONS

Using internationally recognized guides, it was possible to design GFRP reinforced beams with the same failure load than steel reinforced beams. This was useful to compare the general behaviour of both types of beams. However, in real applications, in GFRC elements the design may be controlled by serviceability limit states, for which GFRP has lower stiffness than steel.

From the experimental and theoretical results, it can be highlighted that GFRP reinforced beams show larger mean crack separation (1,55 times) than the steel reinforced beams. Also, although the general behaviour of the FRP models represents the experimental results, the relative errors were larger than the obtained for the steel beams. Being both sensitive to the definition of the cracking moment used for the calculations.

CITATIONS

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.